

GUIDANCE, NAVIGATION, AND CONTROL OF IN-ORBIT ASSEMBLY OF LARGE ANTENNAS – TECHNOLOGIES AND APPROACH FOR IOANT

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IOANT is an on-going activity supported by the European Space Agency aimed at the development of a versatile autonomous Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) system for in-orbit assembly (IOA) of large antennas.

The target is to advance the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of key GNC technologies to 4. To reach this, the activity is structured into two phases:

Phase 1 consists in the definition of a feasible end-to-end in-orbit assembly scenario, including vehicles, mechanisms, and interfaces. A complete GNC solution will be developed and validated using an integrated, coherent, and incremental detailed design, validation, and verification approach.

Phase 2 will advance the GNC solution by designing and performing a series of end-to-end proof of concept tests in a suitable ground facility, using a scaled-down version of the scenario studied in phase 1 and scaling back up the conclusions.

The technologies proposed to be studied can be applied to the assembly of a wide variety of antenna missions, also telescopes and, in a more general sense, mission where the assembly of structures is present.

This paper presents: an introduction to the topic of In-Orbit Assembly with a focus on the benefits and the challenges of this technology; the current state of the art and the proposed scenario – mission, system, and the GNC architecture and proposed concepts.

I. INTRODUCTION

Enhancements in the communications capacity of future satellites can be achieved by increasing the reflector surface area, producing narrower beams. Current and projected missions rely on foldable or deployable antenna concepts to provide larger reflective surfaces, but these systems are limited by the launcher capabilities both in terms of mass and volume.

A natural solution to the limitations imposed by a single launch is to split the payload into several launches, and

then perform in-orbit assembly (IOA) operations. This is becoming possible in part thanks to the latest advances in on-orbit servicing and are the key to unlock the future of communications in space.

In-orbit assembly presents several benefits. It permits the construction of structures that do not fit into a single launcher, even opening the door to structures that could not be created on ground because of the limitations imposed by gravity. It can also increase the longevity and reliability of missions by replacing faulty, damaged, or outdated elements. There are also potential cost-savings, by reducing the mass required for protection and deployment mechanisms, and reducing ground testing.

However, in-orbit assembly also presents several challenges that are currently being studied, both in terms of the system and in terms of the GNC. From the point of view of the system, such a mission requires multiple vehicles to transport and assemble modular segments; it is also expected to have contacts between several elements, which requires the use of manipulators and locking and interlocking mechanisms and introduce disturbances during the assembly process. The main GNC challenges appear in the Control department; the structures will experience large changes in physical properties as the assembly goes on, particularly in the mass-inertia (MCI) properties and the flexible properties. The developed control system needs to take those variations into account and be robust to uncertainties.

II. STATE OF THE ART

In-space assembly missions (from [1] to [5]) can include:

- **In-space assembly of very large reflectors:** radar satellites, telecom satellites and interplanetary probes missions require very large reflectors for enhanced communication capabilities, respectively in terms of absolute output power/EIRP, bandwidth or simply to

manage very long distances. Some of these missions require reflectors with diameters larger than 10 meters and are already using deployable antennas which implies complexity and high risks of a failed deployment. Moreover, due to the difficulty to reproduce zero-gravity testing on-ground, such solutions are complex to qualify. In-space assembly of reflector modules is a suitable alternative to the current risky solutions and enables going beyond the physical limits of the current systems.

- **In-space assembly of mirrors/reflectors:** the size of the primary mirror is of paramount importance for the optical performance of observation and science missions by enabling more signal to be collected by the spacecraft for higher resolution or also better detection of faint objects. The James Webb Space Telescope is a good example of such application with a deployable structure and realignment mechanisms to compensate for alignment mismatch and thermo-elastic effects dynamically. Alignment considerations are a key driver for this application, with performance levels far exceeding the intrinsic in-space assembly capabilities. Local servomotors will need to fine-tune the alignment of the reflective surface with respect to the structure for accurate calibration and dynamic repointing capabilities after assembly.

- **In-space reconfiguration of modular spacecraft:** This concept focuses on performing on-orbit-servicing operations such as maintenance repairs or upgrades with the aim to increase lifespan, performance or even change the mission objective of a space system. Modular designs are expected to have general positive effects on the overall mission effectiveness by allowing re-use of modules across different space products and rapid development of systems. Also, the use of modules of standard sizes with standard interconnects among them can bring additional benefits by introducing flexibility in the assembly of the modules not only in space reconfiguration but also on ground production. An in-space assembly system can provide capability to install, remove and replace ORUs with versatility and the possibility of moving across any serviced structure, provided that enough standard interconnects are available for robotic motion/locomotion purposes. Examples of modular spacecraft are space stations such as MIR, ISS and the Lunar Gateway.

- **Other methods of realizing large baseline antennas and telescopes:** apart from reflectors and mirrors, other applications require very large structures that can hardly be deployed in space directly with monolithic structures. We can count stereoscopic missions (FLEX), large aperture missions (DARWIN) and X-ray telescopes (XEUS, Simbol-X, ATHENA). These missions require big size systems and have been designed as formation flying missions. This application is beyond the primary scope of IOANT, but it has to be kept in mind that many of the IOANT system can also contribute to such

missions by providing automated assembly process. This provides a new option for implementing big-size future missions. In fact, researchers at Caltech/JPL consider space missions that feature a mix of formation flying and on-orbit assembly [6] as a possibility.

III. CASE STUDY

The proposed system for study is the following:

- A Central Module, which centralizes the antenna payload and the antenna AOCs capabilities.
- A transport Tug, which centralizes the rendezvous activities and transports elements between orbits.
- Several stacks of segments, containing the hexagonal antenna segments that compose the antenna surface connected to each other by means of the Standard Interface for Robotic Manipulation (SIROM) [7].
- These segments are relocated using a Multi-Arm Relocatable Manipulator (MARM), a 3-legged robotic manipulator that can walk around the antenna structure [8]

The proposed system has been defined to fulfil multiple goals:

- It allows to study all the key technologies proposed for the activity: Coordinated manipulator-platform controllers, on-board trajectory planning and optimization, controllers adaptable to large variations of MCI properties.
- It is scalable to arbitrarily large systems.
- It is technically feasible with current or in development technology.

The final system after assembly is an antenna with a diameter larger than 20 meters, made of rigid hexagons assembled into 4 rings, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Final Antenna

These points ensure that the technologies studied in IOANT are applicable to a wide variety of missions and systems, and increase the versatility of the developed GNC. Future missions could pick, reconfigure and simplify parts of it, even if their system does not fully align with this case study.

The scenario proposed for the study is as follows . The Central Module and Tug are launched first and placed into GEO using the launcher upper stage and their own propellant for circularization. The stack of reflectors is placed into an orbit 250 km below GEO by means of an upper stage and circularized using an apogee kick-stage. This orbit is passively safe with respect to the GEO ring considering upper stage dispersions. Launches of stacks are to be performed sequentially. The next launch takes place when the preceding stack has been assembled. The tug autonomously captures the reflector stack, and autonomously docks to the central hub. After the stack is emptied, the Tug sends it to a graveyard orbit and the sequence is restarted. Building on top of the mission and scenario, the concept of operations expands and details the operations to be performed for the assembly of the antenna. This is summarized in Fig. 2.

The rendezvous and assembly are divided into 5 different operations, which are represented in Fig. 3.

- **Orbital translational** operations are all the steps to go from the initial spacecraft orbit to the vicinity (a few hundreds of meters) of the vehicle to be captured. From a high-level perspective, the steps to be performed are the same for approaching the central module and for approaching a stack.
- **Pre-mating** operations are common to both the stack capture and the central module capture and contain the final approach segment and preparations for capture, including preliminary robotic operations.

Figure 2: Mission Launch Strategy

Figure 3: Mission concept of operations

- **Mating with Stack** operations
- **Mating with Tug** operations, including both capture and separation
- **Assembly operations** contains all the steps to assemble the antenna tiles onto the central module using the MARM

IV. PROPOSED GNC

The GNC developed focuses on the Tug, which centralizes the rendezvous operations, and the Central Module attitude determination and control system (ADCS) which controls its attitude during assembly operations.

The modes represent the whole envelope of GNC activities for rendezvous, from orbital phases to mating phases, and including variations for capturing both central module and stack vehicles. When developing the GNC modes, there is a trade-off between number of modes and complexity of transitions. The choice has been to minimise the number of modes and grant more authority to the mode manager and the logic to transition. A GNC mode corresponds to a unique combination of guidance, navigation and control modes. Two GNC modes are different if:

- They use different hardware (e.g. different sets of thrusters)
- They change interfaces (e.g. relative position estimation vs relative pose estimation)
- They change goals or internal architecture (e.g. cartesian controllers vs joint space controllers)

The modes developed for the activity corresponds to an event-driven (E3 autonomy) sequence of operations, where the transitions are triggered after a certain condition has been achieved. It encompasses all operations described in the concept of operations, adding also contingency modes in case of failure during rendezvous.

The sequence of modes can be followed forwards (for approaching a vehicle) or backwards (for retreating and restarting operations), and can be different paths for capturing the Central Module or capturing a Stack.

The GNC contains the algorithms to control the approach, rendezvous and mating.

The **navigation** includes:

- Inertial attitude, estimation of the spacecraft attitude using star trackers and gyroscope.
- Orbit estimation based on initial state and measured manoeuvres
- Relative state estimation, which includes far-range using relative GNSS sensors, mid-range using navigation cameras and range estimation, and close-range based on navigation cameras and estimation of the relative pose between vehicles with markers and/or LEDs. The relative estimation can be used for capturing using the robotic manipulator, or for relocating elements around the structure.

The **control** focuses on the variation of MCI and flexible properties of the vehicles to provide a robust and versatile system. In other words, the control accounts for mass and inertia change during assembly, as well as the natural modes of the antenna flexibility, and impact of the MARM location and movement.

The control system development for IOANT is focused on 3 key aspects:

- AOCS of the antenna while the MARM assembles pieces on the structure, which introduces disturbances and alters its dynamical properties.
- Tug and robotic manipulator coordinated control laws, which are highly non-linear.
- System Identification, which supports the estimation of dynamical properties to improve both performance and robustness by reducing the uncertainty ranges.

This is achieved using the following techniques:

- Adaptable gains to account for the changes in MCI properties, which consider the addition of new elements in the structure or the location of the MARM.
- Adaptable filters (low-pass/notch) to account for changes in the flexible properties of the antenna, such as its natural frequencies based on the addition of new elements and the MARM location.
- Model-based PD/H ∞ control loops for phases which use robotic manipulators, where large masses can be attached to the end of the manipulator to relocate elements.

The **translational guidance** focuses on the impulsive phase of the mission, where most of the propellant expenditure takes place. From a qualitative trade-off, the baseline proposed is a Model Predictive Control (MPC)

Figure 4: MPC scheme

scheme for this function as shown in Fig. 4. This allows to reduce propellant consumption and maximize the number of trips/reduce mission cost.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The current status of the project shows few conclusions and observations:

- The system and mission need to be tailored to the specific target antenna, but there are a few common points that can be studied and become applicable to future missions.
- The proposed scenario and system cover all the target technologies and is technically feasible.
- A series of needs, problems, and potential solutions of IOA missions have been studied.
- The operations have been defined to assemble the antenna, from which the concept of operations, GNC modes and algorithms have been defined.
- One key challenge is to characterise the antenna flexible properties and to model that into a closed-loop simulator.

The next steps of the activity include:

- Implementation of the GNC functions described in this paper into a Simulink model.
- Performing a Validation and Verification campaign, including a Monte Carlo test campaign to ensure robustness to a wide envelope of conditions.
- Design, setup, manufacture and breadboard a scaled version of the IOA solution to End-to-End Proof of Concept in an experimental facility to test elements that are difficult to simulate (e.g. contact dynamics.)
- Adaptation of the algorithms developed in Matlab to the test scenario, with a conversion to C code using an autocoding pipeline, consisting of Model-in-the-Loop, Software-in-the-Loop and Processor-in-the-Loop.
- The resulting test campaign in a ground facility would conclude the activity, scaling the results back to the space scenario.

With these steps, the proposed algorithms would reach TRL 4/5, which is the main goal of the activity.

VI. REFERENCES

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